

(1) indicates the presence of a retroelement, (0) indicates its absence, (d) indicates deletion in critical area, (?) denotes absence of sequence information. IR = intergenic region, INT = intron; Out = outgroup; Tvu = *Trichosurus vulpecula*, Pgy = *Phalanger gymnotis*, Gle = *Gymnobelideus leadbeateri*, Pco = *Pseudochirops corinnae*, Pcu = *Pseudochirops cupreus*, Poc = *Pseudocheirus occidentalis*, Neu = *Notamacropus eugenii*, Mru = *Macropus rufus*, Mfu = *Macropus fuliginosus*, Mgi = *Macropus giganteus*, Sbr = *Setonix brachyurus*, Pci = *Phascolarctos cinereus*, Vur = *Vombatus ursinus*. The markers Tr_vu were extracted from common brushtail possum genome, Gy_1 from Leadbeater's possum, and M_eu from tammar wallaby.